

Studies on complexes of copper and nickel with a Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and isonicotinoyl hydrazide

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Abstract : A series of transition metal complexes with formulae $[M(\text{SIH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]_2$, where $M^{n+} = \text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{2+}$, $n = 2$ and SIH = salicylideneisonicotinoylhydrazone, are synthesized by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and isonicotinoyl hydrazide in the presence of metal ions. The complexes are characterized on the basis of their physicochemical properties. The Schiff base and its metal complexes were screened for their antifungal and antibacterial activities. The copper(II) complex exhibited higher inhibition against microorganisms than the nickel(II) complex.

Keywords : Condensation, Schiff base, complex, paramagnetic, octahedral environment, antifungal.

Introduction

Schiff base, a splendid ligand molecule that contains azomethine group (C=N) which are formed by the condensation of primary amines with aldehydes and ketones, are commonly bound to the metal ions of Cu, Ni, Co, Zn, Fe, Mg, etc.¹⁻⁴. The chemistry of coordination compounds with Schiff base as part of their complex structure extends from mononuclear discrete molecule to polynuclear species. Metal complexes of Schiff bases have played a pivotal role in the field of coordination chemistry. The ligation of Schiff base towards the central metal ion provides extra stability and versatility of the compounds making a greater choice of flexibility. The chelating abilities, analytical and biological applications of these compounds have attracted remarkable attention⁵⁻⁷. Though voluminous research in the field of Schiff base metal complexes have been achieved, isolation of complexes with new ligands have been an ongoing area of interest in research⁸⁻¹⁰.

In continuation of these series of investigation¹¹, attempts have been made to widen the scope of derivatization by providing more flexibility through Schiff base formation with isoniazid containing an amino group and com-

plexation with metal ions. The synthesized novel ligand and its metal complexes were also evaluated for their antimicrobial *in vitro* activity against several bacterial strains¹². Isoniazid is a primary antituberculosis agent, and its medicinal value is expected to increase on complexation¹³⁻¹⁵. Therefore, herein we report the synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of properties of transition metal complexes derived from the combination of isoniazid and salicylaldehyde.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of either Glaxo or Merck grade. Solvents were purified before use and the other reagents were used as such. The complexes were prepared by two different methods^{16,17} as described below. First method (Method-I) involves two step processes i.e. preparation of Schiff base ligand, SIH followed by complexation with corresponding Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions whereas second method (Method-II) involves *in situ* synthesis of metal complexes. However, in both the cases, the complexes of the same stoichiometry were isolated. The metal content of these substances were estimated by adopting the standard procedures^{18,19}. The percentage of nitrogen was calculated by combustion method. The val-

ues obtained were also supported by the semi micro Kjeldahl method. The reflectance spectra of the metal complexes were recorded in Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer. IR spectra of the metal complexes were recorded in a Varian spectrophotometer, Australia, in KBr phase in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The electronic spectra of the ligand as well as its complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer. Gouy method has been adopted in the present investigation to calculate the magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes²⁰. Mercury tetrathiocyanatocobalt(II), $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ was used as the calibrant. The molar conductance measurements were carried out with a Philips conductivity bridge (Model CLO1-06, cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1}) using $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ solution of the complexes in DMF. The intensity ratios of all the complexes are recorded by a Philips Analytical X-ray B. V, PC-APD diffraction software. LSUCRIPC software was used to analyse the XRD data. The ESR spectra were recorded as powdered sample (poly crystalline) on an E-112 EPR spectrometer with field set at 3200G, scan range, $2.0 \times 1\text{ KG}$, modulation frequency 9.44 GHz, receiver gain 10×10^2 and modulation amplitude $0.63 \times 10\text{ G}$.

Method-I :

Preparation of SIH ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$) (1) :

A solution of isoniazid (6.8 g, 0.05 mol) in methanol

(50 mL) was prepared in a 100 mL two necked round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser. It was heated for 10 min to ensure dissolution of isoniazid. Then salicylaldehyde (5.2 mL, 0.05 mol) was added to this solution (Scheme 1). The resulted mixture was refluxed at $75\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h. After that the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. The light yellow solid compound **1** was filtered off and then recrystallized from methanol. The recrystallized solid was dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . The analytical and physicochemical data of compound **1** are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Preparation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{SIH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$ (2) :

A solution of SIH (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) was taken in a two necked round bottom flask. An ethanolic solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.0 g, 0.01 mol) was added slowly to it (Scheme 2). The resulting mixture was then refluxed for 3 h until an intense coloured compound **2** separated out. The analytical and physicochemical data of compound **2** are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Preparation of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SIH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$ (3) :

A solution of SIH (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 mL) was taken in a two necked round bottomed flask. An ethanolic solution of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) was added slowly to it (Scheme 2). The resulting mixture was then refluxed for 3 h until an intense coloured

Scheme 1. Synthesis of compound 1.

Table 1. Analytical and some physicochemical data of complexes

Ligand/ Complex	Colour	Mol. wt.	Metal (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :						Mol. cond.	M.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$)
				Calcd.		Found		Nitrogen			
				Carbon	Hydrogen	Carbon	Hydrogen				
(SIH)	Yellow	241	-	64.72	(65.31)	4.60	(5.04)	17.42	(17.64)	-	157
$[\text{Cu}(\text{SIH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$	Green	640	16.93	46.09	(46.36)	3.46	(3.29)	13.10	(13.43)	3.52	232
$[\text{Ni}(\text{SIH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2$	Red	630	15.38	46.75	(47.98)	3.92	(4.31)	12.58	(13.25)	6.71	243

Scheme 2. Synthesis of compounds 2 and 3.

Table 2. IR data of ligand and metal complexes

Ligand (SIH)	[Cu(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	[Ni(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	Assignments
3225	-	-	$\nu_{O-H} + \nu_{N-H}$
3060	3063	3065	ν_{C-H} of C ₆ H ₅
1685	-	-	$\nu_{C=O}$
1585	1565	1562	$\nu_{C=N}$
1055	1045	1060	$\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{N-N}$
-	865	885	ν_{C-O}
-	445	434	ν_{M-O}
-	492	485	ν_{M-N}

was then refluxed for 4 h. The desired solid compound 3 separated out from the reaction mixture and was washed several times with methanol to achieve the maximum purity.

Results and discussion

The complexes (2 and 3) are highly colored and sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. However, they are soluble in DMF/DMSO, which on long standing un-

Table 3. Structural parameters of the complexes of SIH as determined by XRD

Complex	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	α	β	γ	Class
[Cu(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	17.495	23.082	8.276	90°	90°	90°	Tetragonal
[Ni(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	9.465	14.732	9.239	90°	90°	90°	Tetragonal

compound 3 separated out. The analytical and physico-chemical data of compound 3 are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Method-II :

Preparation of compound 2 :

The stoichiometric amount of isoniazid, salicylaldehyde and Cu(CH₃COO)₂·H₂O were taken in a round bottom flask containing methanol. The resulting mixture was then refluxed for 4 h. Then the desired solid compound 2 separated out from the reaction mixture and was washed several times with methanol to achieve the maximum purity.

Preparation of compound 3 :

The stoichiometric amount of isoniazid, salicylaldehyde and Ni(CH₃COO)₂·4H₂O were taken in a round bottom flask containing methanol. The resulting mixture

dergoes decomposition. They have high melting point above 150 °C. The complexes show low molar conductance values in the range 3–7 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting them to be non-ionic in character.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of compounds 2 and 3 suggest them to be paramagnetic, with magnetic moment values of 2.18 B.M. and 1.46 B.M., respectively²¹ which is less than the normal spin only values. The orbital contribution can be attributed to the setting in π -pathway of super exchange through oxo-bridge. Upon heating the respective compounds 2 and 3 up to 200 °C in an air oven, there were no weight loss suggesting the absence of water molecules in the crystal lattice.

The structures of the complexes have been established from different physicochemical methods as discussed below. The analytical data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of metal complexes **2** and **3** are very complicated. However, attempts have been made to identify bands which provide vital information on the mode of bonding of the ligand with the metals, by comparing their spectra with the ligand and other related reported complexes.

In the ligand spectra, absence of bands due to NH_2 and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ (ketonic) groups clearly indicate the formation of Schiff base. However, a broad band with its centre of gravity at about 3190 cm^{-1} is observed. This may be assigned to the intermolecular hydrogen bonding involving the phenolic OH and NH groups²².

The IR spectra of both the complexes **2** and **3** exhibit a broad band relatively in the region of higher frequency between $3500\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes²³ and the same has also been evidenced by thermal analysis. The broadness of the band has been assigned to the combined $\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ stretching mode of vibrations. A strong band is obtained in the region of $\sim 1565\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes which may be due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ ²⁴. The fundamental frequencies due to C-C and N-N have also been observed in the range of $1060\text{--}1029\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ²⁵. An additional band appears in the range $3080\text{--}3055\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ (phenyl ring)²⁶. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (amidic) stretching vibration is obtained at nearly 1685 cm^{-1} in the ligand which is absent in the complexes. This along with the shift in $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ suggests amido-imidol tautomerism²⁷. Medium intensity bands observed in the region $902\text{--}885\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$. In the lower frequency region bands around $480\text{--}500$ and $440\text{--}423\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$, respectively are observed^{28,29}. The IR spectral data of the complexes are given in the Table 2.

Electronic spectra :

The room temperature magnetic moment value of **2** was found to be 1.46 B.M. The low magnetic moment value of the complex suggests the quenching of magnetic moment arising as a result of super exchange of spin through oxo-bridge. In the electronic spectra of complex **2**, three transitions viz. ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ were expected³⁰ due to J.T. effect. A remarkable feature was observed in the electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes, which showed two bands at 12500

cm^{-1} and 14000 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively under D_{4h} symmetry there by distorted octahedral geometry³¹ for the complex. The band due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ remains practically unobserved probably because of its superimposition with ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ band as suggested by its broadness. Further, non-occurrence of bands below 10000 cm^{-1} in the present Cu^{II} complex ruled out the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo tetrahedral geometry.

The complex **3** is paramagnetic. The electronic spectra of the complex **3** was found to exhibit four bands at 18250 , 20333 , 33456 and 38280 cm^{-1} . The first and second bands were of low intensity, being purely d-d transitions assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively and these indicate *trans*-axial distortion leading to the D_{4h} symmetry around the metal center³². The third band was found to be overlapped by a strong charge transfer transition, while the fourth one is due to inter ligand interactions ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$). These results suggest a near octahedral configuration around the nickel(II) ion. The room temperature magnetic moment value of complex **3** was found to be 2.12 B.M. which is lower than the normal value. This lowering in magnetic moment value is probably due to the presence of an oxo bridge between the two metal centres.

ESR spectral study :

The ESR spectrum of the present copper(II) complex **2** exhibited well resolved anisotropic signal in parallel and perpendicular ${}^{63}\text{Cu}$ region. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are $g_{||}$, 2.34; g_{\perp} , 2.08; g_{av} , 2.18; $A_{||}$, $184 \times 10^{-4}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and A_{\perp} , $107 \times 10^{-14}\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The covalency parameter, α^2 was calculated³³ from $g_{||}$, g_{\perp} and $A_{||}$ values and found to be 0.92. The observed data shows that $g_{||}$ and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2 and $g_{||} > g_{\perp}$. This suggests major distortion in the complex from O_h symmetry i.e. D_{4h} symmetry. The α^2 value for this complex is commensurate with considerable covalent character in a bonding involving metal ion and ligand^{34,35}.

XRD study :

From the X-ray diffraction studies, unit cell parameters of both Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were found out and presented in Table 3. The values indicated both the unit cell to be tetragonal.

Table 4. Antibacterial screening data of Schiff base and their metal complexes

Compound number	Standard = Gentamycin								
	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)								
	(Concentration in ppm)								
	<i>E. coli</i>			<i>S. aureus</i>			<i>S. fecalis</i>		
	25	50	100	25	50	100	25	50	100
(1) Schiff base (SIH)	12	12	16	-	10	20	-	-	-
(2) [Cu(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	27	31	34	11	12	13	13	13	15
(3) [Ni(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	12	13	16	11	12	15	15	14	15
(4) Standard	20	23	20	10	10	12	18	20	19
(5) DMSO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(-) = Not measurable.

Based on the foregoing observations, the proposed structure of the copper and nickel complexes (2 and 3) are presented below (Fig. 1) wherein, the two water molecules occupy the *trans*-axial positions.

Fig. 1. Structure of metal complexes; where M = Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ and X = H₂O.

Biological activities :

The biological activity of complexes 2 and 3 along with the ligand was carried out. It was observed that Schiff bases exhibited toxic behavior towards bacterial and fungal pathogens. These activities were further enhanced when a metal ion was incorporated into the Schiff base moiety. The higher activity of the metal complexes may be attributed to the metal ions which has immense effect on the normal cell membrane. The polar and non polar properties of the metal chelates make them suitable for permeation to the tissue and cell. Variation in hydrophilicity and lipophilicity decreases the solubility and permeability, making more bioavailability of the substrate. However, in some cases Schiff bases and their complexes with metal ions have similar activity against bacteria and fungi^{36,37}.

Table 5. Antifungal screening data of Schiff base and their metal complexes

Compound number	Standard = Nystatine					
	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)					
	(Concentration in ppm)					
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>T. polysporum</i>		
	25	50	100	25	50	100
(1) Schiff base (SIH)	13	13	15	-	15	19
(2) [Cu(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	-	-	-	11	15	17
(3) [Ni(SIH)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂	-	-	-	12	13	20
(4) Standard	-	-	-	-	-	-
(5) DMSO	-	-	-	-	-	-

(-) = Not measurable.

The observations from Tables 4 and 5 indicate that the compounds are more active than their respective Schiff bases. In some cases, Schiff bases and their complexes have similar activity against bacteria and fungi. Further it is found that the copper(II) complex is more bio-active than the nickel(II) complex. This higher bio activity of the copper(II) complex may be due to the effect of copper metal ion on the normal cell processes³⁸.

Conclusion :

Novel salicylideneisonicotinoylhydrazone derived Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes prepared by two different routes have been reported. The analytical and physicochemical data of these complexes supported them to be of dinuclear in character, paramagnetic and near octahedral environment around the metal ions. Further it was shown that all these complexes bear relatively good antibacterial properties and the Cu^{II} complex was found to have more inhibition character than Ni^{II} complex.

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